

The 2023 Wearable Photoplethysmography Roadmap

Overview

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The widespread use of smart wearables provides opportunity to monitor health at scale in daily life. Wearables such as fitness trackers and smartwatches routinely use photoplethysmography to monitor the arterial pulse wave, from which a wealth of physiological information can be derived. There are a range of potential clinical applications including detecting abnormal heart rhythms, blood pressure monitoring, and population-level disease surveillance. Despite this, wearable photoplethysmography currently has only a limited impact on clinical practice.

In this Roadmap, experts provide their perspectives on the most pressing areas for future development in the field of wearable photoplethysmography. Development areas range from photoplethysmography sensor design, to signal processing, to clinical applications. For each area, the roadmap provides an overview of its status, describes key challenges, and outlines technological advances which could address these challenges.

Timeline

Please review the following timeline. If you anticipate any issues in meeting the deadlines then please contact Peter Charlton.

Now - July: Authors write contributions

July 15th: Deadline for draft contributions

July - August: Internal review of contributions

August 15th: Deadline for internal reviews

August 16th: Feedback from internal review sent to authors

September 12th: Deadline for final contributions

September 30th: Submission to [Physiological Measurement](#)

Author Guidelines

Please familiarise yourself with the Author Guidelines, which are available at: <insert link>

Contact

If you have any questions please contact <name>: <email address>

Confirmed Sections and Contributors

Please see overleaf

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Section	Author(s)
<i>Introduction</i>	
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<i>Hardware</i>	
<section name>	<section author 1> <section author 2> ...
<section name>	<section author 1> <section author 2> ...
...	...
<i>Signal processing</i>	
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